

8-SINF ALGEBRA FANI DARSLARIDA TRIGONOMETIRYA BO`LIMINI INAVATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TASHKIL ETISH

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Algebra fanini o`qitishda innovatsion yondashuvlar” - algebra fani o`qituvchilari malakasini oshirish kursining o`quv dasturi asosida tuzilgan bo`lib, u algebra fani o`qituvchilariga ta`limda zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovatsiyalarning mazmun va mohiyatini ochib beradi. Fanlarni o`rganish uchun kerak bo`ladigan ba`zi mobil ilovalardan namunalarini ko`rib chiqamiz. “Algebra topqirlik” og`zaki hisob-kitob qobiliyatini o`stirish ilovasi. Ilova tez hisoblash uchun mavjud algoritmlarni aks ettiradi. Har bir o`quvchi ularni o`rganishi mumkin, so`ngra nazariy bilimlarni amaliy mashqlarda mustahkamlashi, shu tariqa og`zaki hisoblash amaliy tajribalarini boyitishi mumkin. Bu ilovani yaratuvchilari og`zaki hisobda tarmoqdagi boshqa foydalanuvchilar bilan raqobat qilish imkonini ham hisobga olishgan [1;2]. Algebra fanini o`qitishda noan`anaviy ta`lim yondashuvlari - agar biror tizimni yangilashga qaratilgan faoliyat qisqa muddatli, yaxlit tizim xususiyatiga ega bo`lib, faqatgina tizimdagi ayrim elementlarni o`zgartirishga xizmat qilsa u innovatsiya (yangilanish) deb yuritiladi. Bordi-yu, faoliyat ma`lum kontseptual yondashuv asosida amalga oshirilib, uning natijasi muayyan tizimning rivojlanishiga yoki uni tubdan o`zgartirishga xizmat qilsa, u innovatsiya (yangilik kiritish) deb ataladi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, innovatsiya (inglizcha “innovatsion” – yangilik kiritish) deb muayyan tizimning ichki tuzilishini o`zgartirishga qaratilgan faoliyatga aytiladi. Algebra fanini o`qitishda innovatsion yondashuvlar moduli bo`yicha o`quvushubiy majmua ta`lim oluvchida yangi g`oya, me`yor, qoidalarni yaratish, o`zga shaxslar tomonidan yaratilgan ilg`or g`oyalar, me`yor, qoidalarni tabiiy qabul qilishga oid sifatlar, malakalarni shakllantirish imkoniyatini yaratadigan ta`limga innovatsion ta`lim deyiladi. Innovatsion ta`lim jarayonida qo`llaniladigan texnologiyalar innovatsion ta`lim texnologiyalari yoki ta`lim innovatsiyalari deb nomlanadi.

Sinus, kosinus, tangens va kotangensning ta`riflari birinchi navbatda geometriyada to`g`ri burchakli uchburchak tomonlari munosabati orqali berilgan.

To`g`ri burchakli uchburchakdagi o`tkir burchak - bu qarama-qarshi oyoqning gipotenuzaga nisbati.

kosinus to`g`ri burchakli uchburchakdagi o`tkir burchak - qo`shni oyoqning gipotenuzaga nisbati.

tangens to`g`ri burchakli uchburchakdagi o`tkir burchak - bu qarama-qarshi oyoqning qo`shnisiga nisbati.

Kotangent to`g`ri burchakli uchburchakdagi o`tkir burchak qo`shni oyoqning teskarisiga nisbati deb ataladi.

Ushbu ta`riflar faqat o`tkir burchaklar uchun amal qiladi (0° dan 90 ° gacha).

Asosiy trigonometrik formulalar

Trigonometriyadagi ko`pchilik formulalar ko`pincha o`ngdan chapga va chapdan o`ngga qo`llaniladi, shuning uchun siz ushbu formulalarni shu qadar yaxshi o`rganishingiz kerakki, ba`zi formulalarni ikkala yo`nalishda ham osongina qo`llashingiz mumkin.

$$\operatorname{tg} x = \frac{a}{b} = \frac{\sin x}{\cos x}$$

$$\operatorname{ctg} x = \frac{b}{a} = \frac{1}{\operatorname{tg} x} = \frac{\cos x}{\sin x}$$

Asosiy trigonometrik identifikatsiyadan eng oddiy xulosalar:

$$\operatorname{tg}^2 x + 1 = \frac{1}{\cos^2 x} \quad \operatorname{ctg}^2 x + 1 = \frac{1}{\sin^2 x}$$

Ikki burchakli formulalar. Ikki burchak sinusi:

$$\sin 2x = 2 \sin x \cdot \cos x = \frac{2 \operatorname{tg} x}{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 x}$$

Ikki burchakli kosinus: $\cos 2x = \cos^2 x - \sin^2 x$

Ikki burchakli tangens:

$$\operatorname{tg} 2x = \frac{2 \operatorname{tg} x}{1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 x}$$

Ikki burchakli kotangent:

Qo'shimcha trigonometrik formulalar

$$\operatorname{ctg} 2x = \frac{1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 x}{2 \operatorname{tg} x} = \frac{\operatorname{ctg}^2 x - 1}{2 \operatorname{ctg} x}$$

Trigonometrik qo'shish formulalari.

Yig'indining sinusi. $\sin(x+y) = \sin x \cdot \cos y + \sin y \cdot \cos x$

Farq sinusi. $\sin(x-y) = \sin x \cdot \cos y - \sin y \cdot \cos x$

Yig'indining kosinusu: $\cos(x+y) = \cos x \cdot \cos y - \sin x \cdot \sin y$

Farq cosinusi. $\cos(x-y) = \cos x \cdot \sin y + \sin x \cdot \cos y$

Yig'indi tangensi:

$$\operatorname{tg}(x+y) = \frac{\operatorname{tg} x + \operatorname{tg} y}{1 - \operatorname{tg} x \cdot \operatorname{tg} y}$$

Farq tangensi:

$$\operatorname{tg}(x-y) = \frac{\operatorname{tg} x - \operatorname{tg} y}{1 + \operatorname{tg} x \cdot \operatorname{tg} y}$$

Darajani pasaytirish formulalari.

$$\sin^2 \frac{x}{2} = \frac{1 - \cos x}{2} \quad \cos^2 \frac{x}{2} = \frac{1 + \cos x}{2}$$

$$\operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{x}{2} = \frac{1 - \cos x}{1 + \cos x} \quad \operatorname{ctg}^2 \frac{x}{2} = \frac{1 + \cos x}{1 - \cos x}$$

Yarim burchak formulalari.

Trigonometrik qisqartirish formulalari

$$\operatorname{tg} x = \frac{\sin 2x}{1 + \cos 2x} = \frac{1 - \cos 2x}{\sin 2x} \quad \operatorname{ctg} x = \frac{1 + \cos 2x}{\sin 2x} = \frac{\sin 2x}{1 - \cos 2x}$$

Kosinus funksiyasi deyiladi **kofunktsiya** sinus funksiyasi va aksincha. Xuddi shunday, tangens va kotangens funksiyalar kofunktsiyadir. Qisqartirish formulalarini quyidagi qoida sifatida shakllantirish mumkin:

- Agar qisqartirish formulasida burchak 90 gradus yoki 270 gradusdan ayirilsa (qo'shilsa), u holda qisqartirilgan funksiya kofunktsiyaga o'zgaradi;
- Agar qisqartirish formulasida burchak 180 gradus yoki 360 gradusdan ayirilsa (qo'shilsa), u holda qisqartirilgan funktsiyaning nomi saqlanib qoladi;

Bunda kamaytirilgan funksiya oldidan olib tashlangan (qo'shilgan) burchakni o'tkir deb hisoblasak, kichraytirilgan (ya'ni asl) funksiya tegishli chorakda ega bo'lgan belgisi qo'yiladi.

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